

Optical phase transition in semiconductor quantum metamaterials

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By stacking subwavelength-thick metallic and dielectric layers to form metamaterials, it is possible to realize unexpected behavior such as negative refraction. Here we report on the optical phase transition in quantum metamaterials based on heterostructured semiconductors. By controlling the stack design, all the possible optical behaviors can be tuned, ranging from classical dielectric and metal to hyperbolic metamaterial type 1 and 2. This tunable response is achieved thanks to intersubband transitions that act as an adjustable resonance to reach negative refraction.

17 Metamaterials are artificial, human designed-materials that feature uncommon physical properties such as
18 ultra-high refractive index, extraordinary optical activity and generalized reflection and refraction [1-5]. In
19 modern optics these metamaterials are becoming ubiquitous, in particular owing to their fascinating
20 possibility of realizing devices based on negative index of refraction. Originally, materials with negative
21 refraction index have been theoretically considered by Veselago in 1968 [6]. The negative index is obtained
22 in a material presenting simultaneous negative dielectric permittivity and magnetic permeability. In
23 Veselago's method, metamaterials are designed by matching electric and magnetic resonances, leading to
24 a strong absorption. Since then, much effort has been made to reduce this absorption, considering for
25 example gain materials [7,8]. Another efficient approach consists in exploiting the hyperbolic dispersion of
26 light propagating in materials featuring opposite signs of permittivity along the orthogonal in- and out- of
27 plane directions [9]. A hyperbolic dispersion is reached in an anisotropic medium by modifying the optical
28 response along one direction, using for example an arrangement of materials of opposite sign of
29 permittivities. In such a system, also dubbed hyperbolic metamaterial (HMM), one of the electric or
30 magnetic resonances is replaced by the material anisotropy. This conceptual simplification comes with a
31 drastic reduction of the optical losses since the main idea is to use an alternating composition of resonant
32 and non-resonant materials. Semiconductor materials offers several functional advantages for HMMs by
33 substituting the metallic resonant part with a highly doped semiconductor [10-12]. Unfortunately, one of
34 the most important feature of a semiconductor heterostructure has been disregarded so far, *i.e.* the
35 quantum confinement and the related electronic transitions.

36 In this letter, we address the fundamental role of a quantum heterostructure inserted in a HMM. Contrary
37 to the previous works on semiconductors HMM, our contribution accounts for not only the in-plane
38 metallic response but also the presence of strong electronic resonances along the z-direction due to the
39 intersubband (ISB) transitions in quantum wells (QWs). Tuning both the QW thickness and the barrier
40 height allows us to tune the optical phase diagram, ranging from classical dielectric and metal to type 1 and
41 2 hyperbolic metamaterial.

42 Before getting into the details of the metamaterial designs, we propose an intuitive toy model that contains
43 all the physical ingredients leading to the HMM. Let us consider a stack composed of two alternating
44 materials: (1) a non-dispersive dielectric and (2) a layer exhibiting a resonant Lorentzian response (see
45 Fig.1a). The resonant medium is represented by an oscillating charge on a spring. In the hyperbolic regime,

46 the thicknesses of both layers - namely l_1 and l_2 - are subwavelength and, thus, the permittivity of the whole
 47 structure can be described using the Maxwell-Garnett effective medium theory. Then the effective
 48 permittivity of the structure can be averaged from the layer medium permittivities (ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 respectively)
 49 as follows:

$$\epsilon_{in-plane} = \frac{l_1 \epsilon_1 + l_2 \epsilon_2}{l_1 + l_2} ; \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_z = \left(\frac{\frac{l_1}{\epsilon_1} + \frac{l_2}{\epsilon_2}}{l_1 + l_2} \right)^{-1} . \quad (2)$$

50 Keeping ϵ_2 constant, a sign inversion of ϵ_1 is required to achieve opposite signs of the in- and out-of-plane
 51 permittivities. A Lorentzian susceptibility can become negative by introducing any physical phenomon that
 52 can be described as a harmonic oscillator mode such as dipole excitations, 2 level quantum transitions or
 53 other effects (see supplementary materials). Taking ω_0 to be the resonance frequency of medium 1 and γ
 54 its broadening, we can write:

$$\epsilon_1(\omega) = \epsilon_\infty + \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_0^2 - \omega^2 - i\omega\gamma} , \quad (3)$$

55 Where ω_p represents the collective oscillation frequency of the ensemble of springs in medium 1 and ϵ_∞
 56 its high frequency permittivity. The optical phase diagram is obtained by substituting equation (3) in (1) and
 57 (2). It exhibits a phase transition from dielectric to metal, through type 1 and 2 hyperbolic metamaterials
 58 as shown in Fig.1b. The sign inversion conditions of the real part of the permittivity are highlighted for both
 59 components in the figure. An intersection between these two curves occurs, giving rise to a hyperbolic
 60 zone. The in-plane resonance occurs at $\omega = \omega_0$. Along the z axis it occurs at:

$$\omega = \sqrt{\omega_0^2 + \frac{\omega_p^2}{\epsilon_\infty}} . \quad (4)$$

61 It represents the maximum excitation frequency to achieve a hyperbolic behavior for negligible absorption
 62 ($\gamma \ll \omega_p$). A negative index of refraction can occur when the composite material reaches type 1 hyperbolic
 63 dispersion [11,13-15]. In such a material, an incoming light beam is refracted with a negative angle, *i.e.*, in

64 the opposite direction with respect to the refracted beam at the interfaces with conventional materials, as
 65 presented in Fig. 1c.
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67
 68 **Figure 1. (a)** Schematic of the toy model structure: a stack along the z direction of 2 alternating media: **layer**
 69 **1**, thickness l_1 and a resonant permittivity ϵ_1 ; **layer 2**, thickness l_2 , dispersionless with a permittivity ϵ_2 . **(b)**
 70 Optical phase diagram showing the sign inversion conditions for both in-plane and z components of the
 71 effective permittivity as a function of the normalized frequency ω/ω_p and of the thickness ratio. 3D inset
 72 images: isofrequency surfaces plotted in k space for the different behaviors. The resonance energy is $\omega_0 =$
 73 $\omega_p/2$. For simplicity the curves are plotted imposing $\epsilon_2 = \epsilon_\infty = 1$ and $\gamma = 0$. The filled regions denote the
 74 parameter space in which in-plane or/and out of plane permittivities are negative. **(c)** Comparison between
 75 the refraction effect in a conventional (right) and in a negative index material (left).

76
 77 The HMM behavior can be experimentally realized with ISB transitions in QWs. Let us consider a multiple
 78 quantum well (MQW) with highly doped QWs and undoped barriers with a spatial period $\Gamma \ll \lambda$, where λ
 79 is the wavelength of light. Due to the confinement in the z-direction, the electrons can oscillate between
 80 two discrete electronic states at a frequency $\omega_0 = \omega_{12}$, behaving as a 2-level quantum system. For sake of
 81 clarity, Fig. 2 shows the results for a thin QW (2.5 nm), in which only 2 levels are present. The oscillator
 82 frequency ω_{12} and, by turn, the Lorentzian resonance frequency in Eq. 3 is tuned by the QW thickness and

83 barrier height. Due to the selection rules, the intersubband transition is dipole forbidden in the in-plane
84 direction ($\omega_{12}^{in\ plane} = 0$) [16]. Therefore the QW permittivity is anisotropic.

85 In order to demonstrate this novel approach, $(10\bar{1}0)$ ZnO/(Zn,Mg)O MQWs have been chosen for the
86 following reasons: 1) The ISB transitions from multiple quantum wells have been demonstrated [17]; 2)
87 High quality non-polar ZnO heterostructures can be grown on bulk ZnO substrates, which facilitates the
88 control of the ISB transitions by avoiding the quantum confined Stark effect [18]; and 3) ZnO can be highly
89 doped, well above 10^{19} cm^{-3} [19,20]. The structures were grown by molecular beam epitaxy on m -plane
90 ZnO substrates. They consist of a 10-period ZnO/Mg_{0.35}Zn_{0.65}O MQW. The ZnO QWs are n -doped ($[Ga] \sim$
91 $5 \cdot 10^{19}$ cm^{-3}) and the Mg_{0.35}Zn_{0.65}O barriers are non-intentionally doped. The doping concentration is high
92 enough for the in-plane susceptibility to be metallic. Since the barrier is undoped, it is considered as an
93 isotropic dielectric material.

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96 **Figure 2.** (a) Band structure for a 2.5 nm thick ZnO QW, including energy levels and Fermi energy (E_f). The
97 blue curves represent the electron wavefunctions. Real (b) and imaginary (c) part of the dielectric function
98 of a 2.5 nm-thick ZnO quantum well along both in-plane and out of plane (z-direction) as a function of the
99 wavenumber with an electron concentration of 5×10^{19} cm^{-3} . The resulting permittivity is also shown for
100 an equivalent ZnO layer with no ISB transition, i.e, setting $\omega_{12} = 0$.

101

102 In order to model the response of a ZnO/(Zn,Mg)O multilayer in the mid-IR, a permittivity that accounts for
 103 the interaction of light with both the lattice vibrations and the electron plasma[21] should be considered.
 104 Here, the ISB resonance is chosen far from the phonon modes ($\omega_{phonons} \leq 675 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Thus the influence
 105 of the phonon modes can be neglected. The dielectric permittivity of the (Zn,Mg)O barrier is nearly isotropic
 106 and can be expressed by $\epsilon^{MgZnO} = \epsilon_{\infty}^{MgZnO}$, where $\epsilon_{\infty}^{MgZnO}$ is the high-frequency dielectric constant. In the
 107 doped ZnO QWs, the isotropy is not preserved anymore due to the presence of the electronic transitions.
 108 More specifically, the high doping concentration in the ZnO layer results in the presence of a quasi 2-
 109 dimensional electron gas in the x-y plane, behaving as a metallic thin-film described by a Drude term in the
 110 permittivity, as:

$$\epsilon_{in-plane}^{ZnO}(\omega) = \epsilon_{\infty}^{ZnO} - \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega^2 + i\omega\gamma_{in-plane}^p}. \quad (5)$$

111 The parameter $\gamma_{in-plane}^p$ stands for the broadening of the plasma resonance at frequency ω_p given by

$$\omega_p^2 = \frac{n_{2D}e^2}{m^*L_{QW}\epsilon_0}, \quad (6)$$

112 where n_{2D} is the 2DEG concentration in the QW, ϵ_0 is the permittivity of vacuum, e is the electron charge,
 113 m^* is the electron effective mass, and L_{QW} is the quantum well width.

114 Along the growth direction, the optical response must take into account the ISB transition. This effect is
 115 well captured by considering an oscillation of the electrons between the 2 sublevels in the conduction band
 116 [16,22,23]. This contribution can be modeled by considering a Lorentzian term in the permittivity, as

$$\epsilon_z^{ZnO}(\omega) = \epsilon_{\infty}^{ZnO} + \frac{f_{12}\omega_p^2}{\omega_{12}^2 - \omega^2 - i\omega\gamma_{12}} \quad (7)$$

117 where f_{12} is the ISB transition oscillator strength, ω_{12} the ISB transition frequency, and γ_{12} its broadening.

118 The effect induced by the ISB transition on the permittivity is presented in Fig. 2, where both the in-plane
 119 and the z-direction components are shown for a ZnO MQW with two confined sublevels. While the in-plane
 120 component of the permittivity is unaffected by the presence of the ISB resonance (dashed lines in Fig. 2b
 121 and c), the presence of ISB transition breaks the symmetry of the bulk optical response in the z direction,
 122 which can be tuned by the layer thickness. As the QW width is increased, the number of sublevels in the
 123 QW increases, and ISB transitions between different levels could occur. Nevertheless, in presence of high

124 doping level, many body interaction effects induce a coherence in the system, leading to a single strong
125 dipole resonance, in which all dipoles in the different transitions are coupled and oscillate resonantly in
126 phase. A mechanical analogue is the motion of the center of mass of an array of particles attached to each
127 other by springs and oscillating in phase. The effective single resonance arising from the mode locking of
128 ISB dipoles that contribute by their oscillation strengths is dubbed multisubband plasmon (MSP) mode
129 [24,25]. Since the MSP mode can be represented by an oscillation between two virtual confined levels in
130 the QW, the single Lorentzian resonance model with the permittivity function in equation (7) is still valid.
131 However, the mode frequency (ω_{12}) and the plasma frequency (ω_p) need to be adjusted as a function of
132 the individual ISB transitions to capture correctly the MSP response[21]. A high doping level in the QWs
133 leads to an additional shift of the ISB absorption peak (ω_{abs}), such that $\omega_{abs}^2 \cong \omega_{12}^2 + \omega_p^2/\epsilon_\infty$ [26]. This
134 effect is known as the depolarization shift, and results from the screening of the electric field by the
135 oscillating electrons in the system. Therefore, the final ISB absorption from the QW is not only a function
136 of the energy difference between sublevels, but also of the electron concentration in the layer. A
137 comparison of this expression with Eq. (4) for a metamaterial where $Re\{\epsilon_z(\omega)\} = 0$ (see figure 1b)
138 indicates that the maximum frequency at which the HMM is type 1 appears at the ISB absorption peak
139 frequency (ω_{abs}).

140 Figure 3 displays the spectral dependence of the permittivities for a MQW as a function of the QW thickness
141 calculated by substituting equations (5) and (7) into (1) and (2). Both in plane and out of plane effective
142 permittivities exhibit a sign inversion, given by the curves $Re\{\epsilon_{in-plane}(l_{ZnO}, \omega)\} = 0$ and
143 $Re\{\epsilon_z(l_{ZnO}, \omega)\} = 0$ underlined by the solid white lines in Figs. 3a and 3b. These two white solid curves
144 are plotted together in the diagram in Fig. 3c to illustrate the optical phase transition occurring in this
145 system as a function of the QW thickness and wavenumber. By changing the QW thickness, *i.e.* ω_{12} , we can
146 obtain all the possible optical behaviors, ranging from classical dielectric and metal to HMM type 1 and 2.
147 The optical phase diagram also shows a singular point where the four optical behaviors meet and where
148 the transition between the optical phases becomes highly sensitive to the system parameters. Remarkably,
149 changing the ISB transition energy allows us to tune the HMM type 1 optical response by around 50 % of
150 the bulk plasma resonance, *i.e.*, by around 1000 cm^{-1} , just by modifying the QW thickness. As opposed to
151 bulk materials without ISB transitions (*i.e.* with $\omega_{12} = 0$), the optical phases can be modified here without

152 changing the plasma frequency of the system. This ability to tune the resonance energy is a unique
 153 characteristic of this type of quantum metamaterial. For large QW widths, the out of plane permittivity
 154 converges to its bulk material value. In this limit, the MSP mode frequency tends to zero, and its plasma
 155 frequency to the bulk plasma frequency of the ZnO layer ($\sim 2250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The optical phase diagram of this
 156 system can also be controlled by adjusting the barrier height, which impacts ω_{12} . In our material system,
 157 this parameter is determined by the Mg concentration in the barrier. Performing the equivalent analysis to
 158 Fig. 3, we show that varying the Mg concentration in the (Zn,Mg)O barrier from 0 to 40 % can tune the
 159 HMM type 1 behavior by up to 780 cm^{-1} (see supplemental material).

160

161 **Figure 3.** Hyperbolic metamaterial condition with a nominal doping of $n \sim 5 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $l_{\text{ZnO}}/l_{\text{MgZnO}} =$
 162 **3.** (a,b) Real part of the effective permittivity out-of-plane (a) and in-plane (b) as a function of the frequency
 163 and QW thickness. The white solid curves show the sign inversions. (c) Optical phase transition diagram of
 164 the system as a function of frequency and QW thickness. The dotted line indicates the position of the grown
 165 sample, with T1 HMM behavior from 1500 to 2150 cm^{-1} .

166

167 To test the validity of our theoretical model, a MQW structure has been grown with a designed
 168 depolarization-shifted ISB resonance at $\omega_{\text{abs}} \approx 2150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The thicknesses were set at 35 nm and 10 nm
 169 for the QWs and the barriers, respectively. The MQW fulfils the requirements for a type 1 HMM ($\epsilon_{\text{in plane}} > 0$
 170 and $\epsilon_z < 0$) in the range from around 1500 to 2150 cm^{-1} (figure 3c). Figures 4a and 4b show the relative
 171 transmittance (ratio of half-blocked to unblocked transmittance spectra; see Methods in supplementary
 172 materials) measured under p and s polarization, respectively, as a function of the angle of incidence on the
 173 HMM. The negative refraction is expected to give rise to a dip or an increase in the relative transmittance
 174 spectra as schematically presented in Fig. 4c and 4d. The relative transmittance measured under p
 175 polarization (Fig. 4a) features a strong variation of the transmission across the frequency band centered at

176 2150 cm^{-1} (i.e. around ω_{abs}). As predicted by the model, this effect is not present when repeating the
 177 experiment under s polarization of the light (Fig. 4b). Moreover, the sign and the intensity of the effect
 178 matches what is predicted for this experiment: for negative angles of incidence, the relative transmission
 179 increases with decreasing angles, whereas for positive angles it decreases with increasing angle. This result
 180 is a direct indication that the MQW structure features negative index of refraction at the frequency of the
 181 ISB resonance. Also note that the observed increase in the relative transmittance for the negative incident
 182 angles indicates that we are observing negative index of refraction and not just absorption from the ISB
 183 transition.

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185

186 **Figure 4.** Ratio of the half-blocked to the unblocked transmittance spectra for p **(a)** and s **(b)** polarizations
 187 of the incoming light. The spectra at normal incidence have been taken as a baseline and subtracted from
 188 all other spectra. The arrows indicate the overall evolution of the spectra with the angle of incidence of the
 189 light. Note the evolution in the s polarized case is non-monotonous. **(c,d)** Schematics of the negative index
 190 of refraction experiment. The transmittance spectrum is measured with a blade blocking half of the
 191 transmitted beam for a range of angles of incidence and normalized by the transmittance spectrum in the
 192 absence of the blocking blade. Depending on the sign of the angle of incidence, two situations are expected:
 193 **(c)** the negatively-refracted beam is deviated from the blade, thus increasing its transmittance, while in **(d)**
 194 for a positively refracted one the transmittance is expected to decrease. This gives rise to a maximum or a
 195 minimum on the blocked-to-unblocked transmittance spectra ratio as a function of the incident angle,
 196 explaining the behavior in **(a)**.

197

198 In conclusion, we have predicted and experimentally demonstrated that the electronic transitions in a
199 quantum semiconductor system lead to hyperbolic behavior. The out-of-plane contribution of the
200 intersubband transition in the QW permittivity enables a type 1 hyperbolic dispersion responsible for the
201 negative refraction. This work connects for the first time the concepts of intersubband plasmons with the
202 photonic response of hyperbolic metamaterials. Both the quantum well and barrier thicknesses and their
203 respective doping are determinant for controlling the electronic resonance used to finely tune the material
204 dispersion. This work highlights the role of quantum confinement in the photonic response of quantum
205 heterostructured materials, and proves that the electronic intersubband resonance in some of the most
206 conventional heterostructured materials could lead to unexpected metamaterial behavior such as optical
207 phase transitions. These results could be used to further control the photonic response and the dispersion
208 properties of various quantum devices using intersubband transitions such as quantum cascade lasers and
209 quantum well infrared detectors.

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